

How to write a data availability statement: A brief guide

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Purpose

This guide provides information on how to write detailed data availability statements (DAS) in preprints and journal articles. DAS are used to communicate if data is available, where they are stored, how access is evaluated/granted, and if data is not available, why access is restricted. The guide applies to researchers who are depositing data publicly, or those who have restricted data that can only be made available under certain conditions.

Data availability statement components

The table below provides recommendations on the level of detail that should be included in a DAS when data are being made publicly available or made available with restrictions. It includes specific recommendations, guidance on what information to include, example language, and whether the information should be provided for data made publicly available, data made available with restrictions, or both.

Component	Guidance	Example language	Public data	Data w/ restrictions
Description of data	Briefly describe the data, including but not limited to type(s) and characteristics (e.g., geography, population, time period), if applicable.	" 2025 survey data collected from Canadian researchers about their data sharing practices are available."	X	X
Location of data	Describe the location where your data can be found and accessed and/or are securely stored. This may be a data repository, institutional servers, a study website, etc.	"Anonymized survey data are available in the Federated Research Data Repository... "	X	X
Link to data	Include a persistent link to where your data are stored. A digital object identifier (DOI) or a URL handle containing a DOI is considered best practice for preservation purposes.	"...data are available in the Federated Research Data Repository via https://doi.org/10.5454/JPSv1i220161014 [artificial URL]"	X	(X) ¹
Data documentation	Describe the documentation provided alongside the data to indicate that they can be easily understood and reused, if applicable.	"The survey instrument , a codebook , and a README file are included with the data."	X	(X) ²
Eligibility criteria	Outline the necessary qualities or conditions that would need to be present for your data to be made available to another person or party.	" Researchers with an active affiliation to a research institution are eligible to request access to these data."		X
Conditions for use	Describe what a person or party can and/or cannot do with the data if they can be made available. This can include but is not limited to following licensing guidelines, acquiring ethics approval,	"Researchers who are granted access will be required to sign a data use agreement and obtain ethics approval from a recognized		X

¹ Note that some restricted data may not have a suitable repository, and therefore no persistent link may be available.

² Note that providing documentation about certain datasets may not be possible if the data are restricted for commercial, ethical, or legal reasons.

	using specific data infrastructure, signing a data use agreement/contract, etc.	research ethics board prior to using these data."		
Access request details	<p>Provide instructions on what a person or party would be required to do to request access to your data. This should include the following, if applicable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The contact information or direct link for where a request should be submitted to, • Application documents that should be submitted (e.g., a research proposal, study protocol, data management plan) including direct links, if available, and • Any costs associated with acquiring the data 	"Access requests should be sent to our institutional data access committee: email@email.com . The request should include a research proposal with a study protocol, an overview of how the survey data would be used, and a data management plan describing how the data will be securely and safely stored over the course of the project, if access is granted. A data processing fee of \$500 will be applied if access is granted. "		X

Examples of data availability statements

This section provides examples of DAS in preprints and journal articles that are separated into three categories: data that are publicly available, data that are available with restrictions, and data that cannot be made available. These examples provide sufficient information to understand where the data are located, how to access the data (if applicable), and the resources provided to help interpret the data.

Publicly available data:

- Raw data from lake withdrawal depths and flow nutrient videos associated with this study are publicly available in the Federated Research Data Repository at <https://doi.org/10.20383/101.0134>. A readme file is included alongside these data.
- Data on person and object recognition sensitivity in musicians and non-musicians are available from the Borealis repository at: <https://doi.org/10.5683/SP3/L8OBJW>. The dataset includes an explanatory memo providing guidance on how to interpret and use the data.
- Fish behaviour data from ocean acidification and live predation experiments, a readme file with an explanation of variables, abbreviations and units, and the analytical code to reproduce the results of this study are publicly available on the Open Science Framework: <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/CZVSF> These materials were shared with the editor and reviewers on manuscript submission.

Data available with restrictions:

- Because of its sensitive nature, population-based birth data will be made available after a data request application is sent to the corresponding author via e-mail: corresponding_author@email.com. Any researcher with active grant funding may submit an application using the following online application form: https://study.com/application_form Applications must include your study design and intended use for the data. A data dictionary is available to review the data variables via the provided link. Involving a local collaborative partner to facilitate the application process is recommended. If your application is successful, you will be required to sign a data transfer agreement.

- Deidentified patient data held by Statistics Sweden and the National Board of Health and Welfare can be made available to authorized researchers with ethical approval. This is in alignment with government data sharing policies. The following links provide:
 - information on the application process, specifically the ethical requirements: <https://etikprovningssmyndigheten.se/for-forskningsperson/>;
 - descriptions of available data: <https://bestalladata.socialstyrelsen.se/data-for-forskning/>; and
 - application documents: <https://www.scb.se/en/services/ordering-data-and-statistics/microdata>.
- Corn e-milling data and their associated model are available from the corresponding author upon request: corresponding_author@email.com. Due to the conditions of the data sharing agreement, these data are only available for educational, research, and non-commercial uses. A request must include all parties who would access the data/model and their roles and describe the intended use of the data in alignment with the criteria outlined above. A codebook can be made available to requestors before an application is made. Successful applicants must sign a data use agreement.
- To maintain sovereignty over the materials collected in this study, geographic data, artwork, and verbal histories analyzed from the First Nations communities described in this study are available upon request and through review by a community approval board. Researchers interested in these data must submit a formal request to the community board via this email: community_board@email.com. The request should include a description of the research project, the intended use of the data and traditional knowledge, how the community(ies) will be engaged in the research project, and the names and roles of all individuals who would access the data. Successful applicants will be required to meet with the community board, sign a research agreement, and complete a data use agreement that follows the OCAP® and CARE principles. The data use agreement ensures that these data are only accessible through community-led digital infrastructure and cannot be redistributed or shared without approval.

Data not available:

- The datasets generated and/or analysed during the current study are not publicly available due to the inclusion of proprietary information on the industrial application produced in collaboration with Company X.
- Data cannot be shared as consent for data sharing was not included in the informed consent process.
- The Indigenous participants in this study have requested that their data not be shared and that it remains within their communities.

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